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ECONOMIC IMPACT OF THE EUROPEAN UNION DEFORESTATION-FREE REGULATION (EUDR) ON THE NATIONAL PALM OIL INDUSTRY

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RESUME

The implementation of the EUDR policy which resulted in the stoppage of trade in palm oil products between the two countries has had an impact on Indonesia's economy, particularly on the trade balance. Without the exports of palm oil products, the Indonesia-EU trade balance will experience a growing deficit. In addition to accelerating the achievement of ISPO in realizing sustainable palm oil, the strategy to overcome the economic impact of EUDR implementation is by expanding the domestic palm oil downstreaming while simultaneously promoting palm oil exports to non-EU markets.

INTRODUCTION

The European Union (EU) has adopted the European Union Deforestation-Free Regulation (EUDR) on 22 April 2023 and it came into effect on 29 June 2023 for all countries supplying forest-risk commodities to the EU market (PASPI Monitor, 2022^{b,c}). The application of this EU regulation to other countries is also known as the Brussels Effect (Bradford, 2020) which has been perceived as arrogant since it bypasses international organizations/provisions/mechanisms, leading some parties to view it as a form of EU regulatory imperialism.

The EUDR prohibits commodities and derivative products related to deforestation, forest degradation, and illegal activities with a cutoff date of 31 December 2020 from entering the EU market. Commodities and derivative products may only enter the EU market if they meet these criteria: (1) being free from deforestation and forest degradation; (2) having sufficient legality in accordance with the laws and regulations in the producing country (production location); and (3) undergoing the due diligence with EU procedures (traceability supply chain, geolocation, risk mitigation based on risk levels, namely low risk, standard risk, and high risk).

Regardless of the regulatory imperialism motive, the implementation of the EUDR increases the risk levels and uncertainty in palm oil trade with the EU market going forward. The EUDR further amplifies the risk and uncertainty of palm oil product exports to the EU, especially after the EU had implemented the RED II/ILUC policy and designed the phase-out of palm oil from the EU's biofuel trade. Therefore, in extreme condition, the EU policy has the potential to stop palm oil trade to the EU, either by the EU itself or by exporters.

The various complexities of problems and risks of uncertainty regarding EUDR implementation include the polemics over the definition of deforestation and forest degradation (PASPI Monitor, 2022^b), the fulfillment of numerous legalities, especially for smallholders, the complexity of the EU version of due diligence, and the high implementation costs which are estimated to increase production costs by 20 percent or more, among other issues. These conditions will lead business players to seek markets outside the EU rather than navigate the complexities of the EUDR, which do

not add to the selling value of traded palm oil products. Thus, the implementation of the EUDR has the potential to hamper, disrupt, and even stop palm oil exports to the EU.

This journal article will discuss the impact if Indonesia's palm oil exports to the EU are stopped due to the EUDR. Apart from the impact, this article will also discuss the strategy that can be implemented to compensate the impact of the EUDR.

PALM OIL EXPORTS TO THE EUROPEAN UNION

The EU market is one of the export markets for Indonesia's palm oil products. However, in the last five years (2018-2022), the EU's share in Indonesia's total palm oil exports to the world has experienced a declining trend. Based on ITC Trademap data (2023), the EU's share in Indonesia's total palm oil exports was still around 16.4 percent in 2018, then decreased to 14.4 percent in 2020, and continued to fall to 12.6 percent in 2022. This indicates that the role of the EU market in the Indonesia's palm oil export market has been decreasing.

The decline in the EU share reflects that palm oil exporters are increasingly reducing their palm oil exports to the EU due to increased risks of palm oil trade to the EU, primarily caused by the EU policies such as RED II ILUC, phase-out, anti-dumping, and others (PASPI Monitor, 2019^{a,b}; Suharto *et al.*, 2019) which are unfriendly towards palm oil. On the other hand, the export markets for Indonesia's palm oil outside the EU have increased, driven by both attractive palm oil market growth and conducive trade policies. In other words, the Indonesia's palm oil industry is no longer dependent on the EU market as its export market has diversified to many countries.

Although the EU market may no longer be crucial for the palm oil industry, it still appears to hold significance for Indonesia's overall economy. The exports of Indonesia's palm oil products to the EU are still an important component in the bilateral trade balance between Indonesia and the EU (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Role of Palm Oil Product Exports in the Trade Balance between Indonesia and the EU (Source: ITC Trademap, data processed by PASPI, 2023)

In absolute terms, the export value of Indonesia's palm oil products to the EU has continued to increase in the last 5 years. The export value of Indonesia's palm oil products to the EU in 2018 was USD 3.8 billion and decreased slightly in 2020 to USD 3.3 billion, and then increased to USD 5 billion in 2021 and 2022. The increase in export value in these two years was mainly driven by the rise in global palm oil prices (PASPI Monitor, 2022^a).

The importance of palm oil product exports in the Indonesia-EU trade balance is evident in the comparison between "Net Trade Without Palm Oil" and "Net Trade With Palm Oil". With Indonesia's palm oil exports to the EU, the Indonesia-EU trade balance enjoys a small surplus or a small deficit. However, without palm oil exports to the EU, the Indonesia-EU trade balance will experience a large

deficit and a tendency for even greater deficit. The increasing deficit in the Indonesia-EU trade balance will occur as a result of the implementation of the EUDR, which will stop Indonesia's palm oil exports to the EU, and no increase in palm oil exports outside the EU.

EUDR IMPACTS

To see the impact of stopping Indonesia's palm oil exports to the EU on the palm oil industry and the Indonesia's economy, a simulation was carried out using a number of simultaneous structural equations. There are three simulated scenarios, namely: (1) Scenario One (S1) which reflects the impact of stopping Indonesia's palm oil exports to the EU; (2) Scenario Two (S2) which represents the expansion of domestic palm oil downstreaming through an increase in CPO absorption of 40 percent from the previous one; and (3) Scenario Three (S3) which depicts a combination of stopping Indonesia's palm oil exports to the EU (S1) but responded by Indonesia through a combination of expanding domestic palm oil downstreaming (S2) and increasing palm oil export promotion to non-EU markets by 20 percent from the previous one. The simulation results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Simulation of the Impact of Stopping Indonesian Palm Oil Exports to the EU and Domestic Palm Oil Downstreaming Response and Promotion of Exports to Non-EU Market

No.	Variable	Change (%)		
		Stoppage of Indonesian Palm Oil Product Exports to the EU by 20% (S1)	Expansion of Domestic Palm Oil Downstreaming by 40% (S2)	Combination of S1, S2, and Increased Palm Oil Product Exports to Non-EU Markets by 20% (S3)
1	FFB Production	-0.16	5.12	5.12
2	CPO Production	-0.11	3.71	3.71
3	Domestic CPO Supply	1.10	4.04	6.24
4	Domestic CPO Demand	0.04	40.00	40.08
5	Indonesian CPO Export	-20.00	0.41	0.41
6	Domestic CPO Price	-0.35	21.15	21.15
7	Global CPO Price	0.01	0.00	0.02
8	Domestic FFB Price	-0.64	24.84	24.84
9	FFB Producer Surplus	-0.13	25.48	25.48
10	CPO Producer Surplus	-1.70	21.55	21.55
11	CPO Consumer Surplus	0.35	25.39	26.09
12	Government Revenue	-23.42	0.48	0.48
13	Net Welfare	-0.60	24.01	24.01

If Indonesia stops palm oil exports to the EU (S1) with the assumption that no response is made to neutralize the impact, it will result in the decline in welfare through decreased surplus for both CPO producers and FFB producers, as well as reduced government revenue due to the decrease in exports to the EU. The amount of reduction in CPO and FFB producer surpluses as well as the decline in government revenue cannot be compensated by an increase in domestic palm consumer surplus, so overall the stoppage of palm oil exports to the EU is slightly detrimental to Indonesia. A study by Rifin *et al.* (2020) has also confirmed that stopping palm oil exports to the EU also has a negative impact on Indonesia, albeit not significantly.

Compared to S1, Scenario S2, which is the expansion of domestic palm oil downstreaming, has been proven to have a positive impact on the palm oil industry and the Indonesia's economy as a whole. The results of this simulation further strengthen that domestic palm oil downstreaming is very profitable for Indonesia because it is included as Indonesia's tool for managing the global palm oil market (PASPI, 2023). The expansion of domestic downstreaming is able to push up the global price of palm oil, which leads to an increase in smallholders' income and an increase in foreign exchange.

If the stoppage of palm oil exports to the EU (S1) is then responded by the national palm oil industry through the expansion of domestic palm oil downstreaming and the promotion of increased palm oil exports to non-EU markets (Scenario S3), it turns out that it is not only able to offset the potential negative impact of the EUDR, but also able to provide even greater benefits for both the national palm oil industry and the Indonesia's economy as a whole.

Therefore, Indonesia does not need to exert excessive energy on addressing the EUDR policy. In extreme condition, where the EU stops importing Indonesian palm oil or Indonesia stops exporting palm oil to the EU, the negative impact can still be mitigated by domestic palm oil downstreaming which has been intensively ongoing since 2011 (PASPI Monitor, 2021; PASPI Monitor, 2023^b). Moreover, if domestic palm oil downstreaming is accompanied by an increase in exports to non-EU markets, it can not only compensate for the EU market but also enhance benefits for both the palm oil industry and the Indonesia's economy as a whole.

The strategic solution above does not mean that Indonesia disregards the positive message of the EUDR concerning the importance of palm oil sustainability. Indonesia and the national palm oil industry remain committed to becoming more sustainable. To achieve this vision, long before the existence of the EUDR, Indonesia has already established sustainable palm oil system and governance and has been on the right track, namely through the ISPO which had existed since 2011 (PASPI Monitor, 2020; PASPI, 2023^a). Improvement in the palm oil industry governance and going forward is not for the EU, but for the future of Indonesia and the world.

CONCLUSION

The EU's role as a destination market for Indonesia's palm oil exports has shown a declining trend. Apart from the result of the EU's own protective policies, the downward trend is also due to the increasingly diversified markets for Indonesia's palm oil exports. On the other hand, the role of palm oil exports in the Indonesia-EU trade balance is still important. Without exports of palm oil products, the Indonesia-EU trade balance will experience a growing deficit.

If the EUDR policy leads to the EU or Indonesia stopping the palm oil trade, the potential negative impact can be mitigated by expanding domestic palm oil downstreaming. If the domestic palm oil downstreaming is accompanied by the promotion of palm oil exports to non-EU markets, it will not only be able to overcome the negative impact due to the EUDR, but can also increase the benefits for the palm oil industry and the Indonesia's economy compared to from before.

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REFERENCES

- Bradford A. 2020. *The European Union in a Globalised World: the "Brussels Effect"*. Columbia Law School. <https://scholarship.law.columbia.edu/books/232/>
- Chain Reaction Research. 2022. *EU Deforestation Regulation: Implications for Palm Oil Industry and Its Financers*. <https://www.chainreactionresearch.com>

- European Economics. 2014. *The Economic Impact of Palm Oil Imports in the EU*. <http://theoilpalm.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/Europe-Economics-Economic-Impact-of-Palm-Oil-Imports.pdf>
- ITC Trademap. 2023. *Indonesia's Palm Oil Products Exports*. <https://www.trademap.org/>
- PASPI Monitor. 2019a. Dampak Penghentian Impor Minyak Sawit Indonesia oleh Uni Eropa. *Monitor*. 5(23): 1541-1546.
- PASPI Monitor. 2019b. Strategi dan dampak pemberlakuan Kebijakan Uni Eropa. *Monitor*. 5(32): 1611-1616.
- PASPI Monitor. 2020. Presidential Regulation On Ispo And Critics Of The Concept Of Palm Oil Sustainability *Palm Oil Journal Analysis of Palm Oil Strategic Issues*. 2(18): 115-122
- PASPI Monitor. 2021. Hilirisasi dan Perubahan Komposisi Ekspor Minyak Sawit Indonesia. *Palm Oil Journal Analysis of Palm Oil Strategic Issues*. 2(13): 351-356. <https://palmoilina.asia/jurnal-kelapa-sawit/sawit-dan-hilirisasi/>
- PASPI Monitor. 2022a. Policy for Stabilizing Domestic Cooking Oil. *Palm Oil Journal Analysis of Palm Oil Strategic Issues*. 3(6): 619-626
- PASPI Monitor. 2022b. "Deforestation-Free" Policies and It's Polemic. *Palm Oil Journal Analysis of Palm Oil Strategic Issues*. 3(15): 683-688.
- PASPI Monitor. 2022c. Response to The EU's Anti-Deforestation Policy on Palm Oil. *Palm Oil Journal Analysis of Palm Oil Strategic Issues*. 3(21): 722-725.
- PASPI. 2023a. *Mitos dan Fakta Industri Minyak Sawit Indonesia dalam Isu Sosial, Ekonomi, dan Lingkungan Global. Edisi Keempat*. Bogor (ID): Palm Oil Agribusiness Strategic Policy Institute.
- PASPI. 2023b. *Kebijakan Hilirisasi Sawit Domestik Merubah Komposisi Ekspor Sawit Indonesia Periode Tahun 2015-2022*. <https://palmoilina.asia/jurnal-kelapa-sawit/kebijakan-hilirisasi-sawit/>
- Rifin A, Feryanto, Herawati, Harianto. 2020. Assessing the Impact of Limiting Indonesian Palm Oil Exports to the European Union. *Journal of Economic Structure*. 9(26). <https://journalofeconomicstructures.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40008-020-00202-8>
- Suharto R, Agus F, Santosa Y, Sipayung T, Gunarso, P. 2019. *Kajian Terhadap European Union Renewable Energy Directive (EU Directive 2018/2001) dan EU Commission Delegated Regulation 2019/807 serta Perumusan Posisi Indonesia terhadap Kebijakan Tersebut*. Jakarta (ID): Kementerian Koordinator Bidang Perekonomian; Badan Pengelola Dana Perkebunan Kelapa Sawit; PT Riset Perkebunan Nusantara.

